

1 Brwd1 controls early transcriptional dynamics for Xist-based epigenetic imprinting in somatic cells.

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

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8 We used transcriptomics to discover 3 major regulators of imprinting-based epigenetic gene control. Here, we describe an early role for BRWD1 in Xist-based epigenetic imprinting in somatic cells.

9 Citations

10 1. Mandal, M., Hamel, K.M., Maienschein-Cline, M., Tanaka, A., Teng, G., Tuteja, J.H., Bunker, J.J., Bahroos, N., Eppig, J.J., Schatz, D.G. and Clark, M.R., 2015. Histone reader BRWD1 targets and restricts recombination to the Igk locus. *Nature immunology*, 16(10), pp.1094-1103.

11 2. Mandal, M., Maienschein-Cline, M., Hu, Y., Mohsin, A., Veselits, M.L., Wright, N.E., Okoreeh, M.K., Yoon, Y.M., Veselits, J., Georgopoulos, K. and Clark, M.R., 2024. BRWD1 orchestrates small pre-B cell chromatin topology by converting static to dynamic cohesin. *Nature immunology*, 25(1), pp.129-141.

12 3. Philipps, D.L., Wigglesworth, K., Hartford, S.A., Sun, F., Pattabiraman, S., Schimenti, K., Handel, M., Eppig, J.J. and Schimenti, J.C., 2008. The dual bromodomain and WD repeat-containing mouse protein BRWD1 is required for normal spermiogenesis and the oocyte–embryo transition. *Developmental biology*, 317(1), pp.72-82.

13 4. Pattabiraman, S., Baumann, C., Guisado, D., Eppig, J.J., Schimenti, J.C. and De La Fuente, R., 2015. Mouse BRWD1 is critical for spermatid postmeiotic transcription and female meiotic chromosome stability. *Journal of Cell Biology*, 208(1), pp.53-69.

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Results

1. GSE32015

mES with inducible expression of BRWD1
n=3 control vs n=6 mES-BRWD1

2. GSE56482

BRWD1 in vivo; testis; 27 days

n=4 BRWD1 +/- vs n=4 BRWD1 -/-